

Loss of an abundant quantity of ribonucleic acid during mini column isolation method

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Summary: Isolation of nucleic acid is an important step for conducting different molecular assays in many laboratories around the world. It is also a common practice that user is isolating the ribonucleic acid (RNA) from the sample with mini column once and throwing away the supernatant. This makes isolated RNA as limiting factor in many studies. In this research, we have made analysis whether there is a loss of RNA during the isolation process as this issue has not been addressed in literature. It was found that there is loss of abundant quantity of RNA during the subsequent isolations. The amount measured with UV spectrometer indicates that some times 2nd and 3rd isolation have more RNA than the first isolation. Realtime PCR for house keeping gene beta actin shows that presence of RNA can be seen up to 6 isolation cycles from supernatants. Conclusion: there is loss of RNA in subsequent isolations, therefore it is possible to isolate more RNA from subsequent supernatant isolations.

Keywords: Mini column isolation, RNA, nucleic acid, PCR, real time PCR. Viruses, Biomarkers, Vaccines

Introduction: Isolation of nucleic acid is an essential step for conducting the different nucleic acid analysis methods like PCR and hybridization for various viral, bacterial, biomarkers and genetic targets. (Lee et al. 2009; Pruvot et al. 2013; Bhatia 2021) Not only this, the nucleic acid can be used as therapeutic as well as vaccine options in many clinical settings, therefore there is an urgent need to isolate the sufficient amount of nucleic acid in highly pure form. (Wolf et al. 1990; Schalke et al. 2012; Kyle et al. 2013; Wadhawa et al. 2020) Ribonucleic acid (RNA) can be isolated from different sources e.g., blood, tissue, buccal swabs, nasal samples, plasma, serum, urine and cell cultures. There are different methods available to isolate the RNA, which are magnetic beads, solutions-based and mini column methods. The mini column isolation method is widely used in laboratories around the world. Usually most of laboratories around the world isolate the RNA from the sample once and the supernatant of this method is discarded. Many times, there is limited volume of isolated RNA e.g., 50 or 100 ul, which is not sufficient to conduct the whole studies, where user has to conduct a set of experiments on the same isolated RNA (homogenous material). In case of development of vaccines, one needs sufficient quantity of RNA, which may not be available from a single isolation source. (Boom et al. 1990; Zhang et al. 2010; Bhatia 2021)

In this study, the experiments are conducted to find whether RNA is still in supernatant and this surplus RNA can be isolated to conduct the further analysis.

Methods: In this experiment, 4 samples from different tissues like umbilical cord, placenta tissue, placenta membrane etc. are used to isolate the RNA with mini column RNA isolation kit (Genekam, Germany). 100 ul of the samples were added to lysis buffer with proteinase K. These samples were

kept at 56 °C for 10 minutes. After that guanidine solution was added, while keeping at 70 °C for 5 minutes. 400 ul of molecular ethanol (Applichem, Germany) was added to each well.

Mini column step: These mixtures were added to mini columns, which were centrifuged at 11000 rpm for 1 minutes. The supernatant from each sample were collected in separate tubes. Mini columns were washed with 500 ul B and C tubes each while centrifuging at 11000 rpm for one minute. At the end mini columns were centrifuged in order to make them dry at 13000 rpm for 1 minute. At last, 70 °C warm elution buffer was added to each mini column, while keeping this for 2 minutes at room temperature. In order to get the elution buffer containing RNA, the mini columns were centrifuged. The tubes were labelled as first isolation and stored at 4 °C for further analysis.

Collected supernatants were processed as mentioned in mini column step till there was use of elution buffer at the end to elute RNA. During this step, the supernatants were collected and processed again as mentioned above. There were two groups. In one group, there were 2 isolations (one original isolation and 1 isolation from supernatants, these are labelled as Isolation 1 and 2) and in 2nd group, there are 7 isolations (one original isolation and 6 isolations from supernatants, which were labelled as Isolation 1 to 7). In both groups, isolation 1 is the original and first isolation and rest isolations are from subsequent supernatants. (Table 1 and 2)

Total Volume of isolated RNA was 50 ul per isolation.

Measurement of RNA content with UV spectrometer, Nanodrop (Thermofischer, USA): The instrument was calibrated with elution buffer. After that, 2 ul of each isolated was measured and the values are recorded at ug / 2 ul.

Real time PCR for human internal control: All isolated samples were tested for the presence of RNA with housekeeping gene called beta actin through real time kit FR799 (Genekam, Germany) in 96 well plate in a real time machine ABI 7500 (Thermofischer, USA). 2 ul of isolated RNA was used during the real time PCR reaction in 18 ul RNA mastermix containing cDNA synthesing enzymes. The temperatures and cycling conditions were one cycle 42 °C for 60 minutes and 70 °C for 10 minutes as well as 45 cycles of 90 °C for 15 seconds and 60 seconds for 60 °C. The results were analyzed with software in linear and log modes along with recording of Ct values.

Results: Group 1, where the 2 isolations were done. The values of these versions of different samples measured with Nanodrop is shown in the table 1. The values indicate that there is loss of RNA during 2 isolations. Therefore, it is decided to conduct second experiment, where the isolation was repeated up to 7 isolations. The results are shown in the table 2. The results indicate that there is a loss of RNA during all steps and this loss decreases with the increase in the number of isolations. In the sample 2, it varies better 0.170 ug / 2 ul at the beginning to 0.006 ug / 2 ul. It was very surprising to see that amount of isolated RNA was more in the first supernatant passage than the first isolation.

Real time PCR of isolated RNA in different isolated versions show that real time for beta actin housekeeping gene is in position to detect RNA in all isolations regardless whatever quantity was detected in Nanodrop. Results are shown as curves in picture 1. It is hard to find any correlation between the amount of RNA measured in Nanodrop and Ct values achieved in the real time machine.

Discussion: Since the availability of possibility to isolate the nucleic acid with mini columns, it has become the common practice in all laboratories working with molecular methods, to conduct the

RNA isolation from different samples to analyze them for different targets as these may be pathogenic agents and biomarkers of different cells e.g., stem cells, tumor cells, immune cells etc. It is also daily practice in the laboratories to measure the presence of viral RNA in different samples. (Silva et al. 2002; Chechlińska et al. 2006; Lee et al., 2010; Othman et al. 2014) Most of the laboratories are doing only once the isolation and throw away the samples as supernatant. Amount of isolated RNA with only one time isolation is very limited e.g., 100 ul. If user is conducting experiments for a number of different targets, this small amount can be a limiting factor because of its small size.

In der Literature, there is hardly any report that some groups have tried to look into this important problem in spite of the fact that each group needs sufficient amount of nucleic acid to conduct the assays from the same source. This study is indicating that it is possible to isolate the more RNA from the supernatants. In this way, many laboratories have sufficient amount of isolated RNA to conduct bigger studies and compare them also. (Honsvall et al. 2017)

There are research groups, which are working on development of vaccines and therapies, they may face many times a challenge to isolate the sufficient to conduct their experimental studies. This publication provides them the way to isolate more amount of valuable RNA rather throwing of the rest of supernatant.

These studies shown here can help many institutes and laboratories to save money in terms of chemicals and time used to isolate the samples. In two samples shown table 2, the amounts of isolated RNA from sample 3 and 4 were less than that of RNA isolated from two following supernatants from the first isolation. It should be investigated further as it indicates that there may be some time a lot of loss of RNA in the first isolation or binding capacity of membrane may be playing a role. User can have more isolated RNA in 2nd and 3rd subsequent isolations.

There are many publications, where research groups are using 5ul or 10ul during the PCR studies, hence a lot of quantity of isolated RNA can be obtained from supernatant, which is usually thrown away as waste product. (Moes et al. 2005; Holbrook et al. 2021) This publication is showing a way to get larger volume of isolated RNA to bigger studies.

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Table 1 : Measurement of UV spectrometer for the concentrations of RNA in different isolations. (Group 1)

Sample *	Isolation 1	Isolation 2
1	0.006	0.009
2	0.053	0.042
3	0.005	0.022
4	0.005	0.09

* µg / 2µl

Table 2 : Measurement of UV spectrometer for the concentrations of RNA in different isolations. (Group 2)

Sample *	Isolation 1	Isolation 2	Isolation 3	Isolation 4	Isolation 5	Isolation 6	Isolation 7
1	0.005	0.003	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.008	0.001
2	0.018	0.007	0.004	0.001	0.001	0.008	0.006
3	0.077	0.163	0.073	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.003
4	0.01	0.4	0.136	0.014	0.002	0.002	0.005

* µg / 2µl

Picture 1 : It is showing the results of real time PCR for internal control for the presence of human RNA in isolated samples.